

ELECTROMYOGRAPHIC BIOFEEDBACK- ASSISTED PELVIC FLOOR MUSCLE TRAINING ON STRESS URINARY INCONTINENCE FOLLOWING CENTRAL & PERIPHERAL NERVOUS SYSTEM VASCULITIS: A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Background and purpose: This case report describes interventions involving pelvic floor muscle training (PFMT) with electromyographic biofeedback (EMG-BFB) for a 52-year-old man with stress urinary incontinence (SUI) following CNS and PNS vasculitis.

Summary: Diagnosed with CNS and PNS vasculitis 5 years back, the patient gradually developed stress urinary incontinence. He was treated with PFMT in adjunct with EMG-BFB for 20 sessions and the pelvic floor muscle strength and the effect of SUI on the quality of life were assessed.

Outcome: Improvements were seen in the pelvic floor muscle strength as measured by the modified oxford grading system; severity of SUI as measured by the International Consultation Incontinence Questionnaire-Short Form; and the Incontinence-Quality of Life that measures the quality of the life following incontinence. A possible cause of improvement in the symptoms following intervention may be due to both the physical as well as the behavioral effect of EMG-BFB when used as an adjunct to the PFMT.

Keywords: Vasculitis, Stress urinary incontinence, PFMT, EMG-BFB

Introduction

Vasculitis is a diversified clinicopathologic disorder that is histopathologically characterized by the inflammation of the blood vessels including veins, arteries, and capillaries that can cause problems in any organ system, including the central (CNS) and peripheral (PNS) nervous systems which are characterized by secondary narrowing of the blood vessels that nourish the brain, spinal cord, or peripheral nerves caused by the presence of inflammatory cells in and around blood vessels [1].

Out of all assorted symptoms associated with CNS or PNS vasculitis or both together, urinary incontinence is one that often has an early onset. Few studies have reported the association of urinary incontinence, especially stress urinary incontinence (SUI) with CNS and PNS vasculitis but they lack to establish the direct link between the two and determine the exact cause [2][3].

SUI is described as “the complaint of involuntary leakage on effort or exertion, or on sneezing or coughing due to the weakness of the sphincter following neurological damage” [4]. Regarding the different therapeutic methods for SUI treatment, biofeedback is considered within the conservative measures as an instrumental technique for pelvic floor muscle training (PFMT) that can be of two types: manometric and

electromyography-biofeedback (EMG-BFB). EMG-BFB is the most used one, based on its efficacy in the treatment of SUI has been proven [5].

Although there is a sufficient number of literature reviews available on the effect of EMG-BFB in populations with SUI, there is very little evidence that can show the effectiveness of PFMT along with EMG-BFB in a male patient with SUI following CNS and PNS Vasculitis. Thus our case study aims to determine the effectiveness of the PFMT protocol with EMG-BFB in a 52-year-old male patient, with stress urinary incontinence due to flaccid bladder following CNS and PNS Vasculitis as well as to determine the potential effect of the treatment on the quality of life of an incontinent male.

Case Description

The subject was a 52 years old male with a chief complaint of difficulty in walking and involuntary micturition and defecation for the last 5 years. He had a clinical history of sudden onset of urine obstruction and abdomen distension on June 23rd, 2016. Within 12 hours he developed weakness in the distal lower limb muscles that gradually progressed proximally within 36 hours. Since then all the symptoms have worsened with time. Based on the clinical findings, investigatory reports, and radiological findings he was later diagnosed with CNS and PNS vasculitis.

On examination, the superficial, deep, and combined cortical sensation was found to be impaired at L₄, L₅, S₁, S₂, S₃, S₄, and S₅ dermatomes. Goniometric evaluation of lower extremity revealed full active and passive hip, knee, and ankle joint range of motion except for hip and knee extension and ankle dorsiflexion which showed tightness of bilateral hamstrings, iliopsoas, adductor group of muscle, and contracture of bilateral gastrocnemius and soleus. He was having increased muscle tone of hip flexors and knee flexors with spasticity of grade 3 and 1+ respectively as per Modified Ashworth Scale. There was moderately impaired coordination with non-equilibrium tests in lower extremities such as heel-knee-shin maneuver, alternate heel to knee, and heel to toe maneuvers. The patient was able to sit without assistance and was able to stand with the support of assistance. He was also able to walk a few steps with the help of a walker.

On bladder and bowel assessment the patient was having impaired sensation at S₃, S₄, and S₅ dermatome and had impaired sensation of filling and subsequently control of bladder and bowel. The patient was on a CIC catheter. The patient was able to hold urine for a few minutes (~ 3 mins) but urinate with any activity involving an increase in abdominal pressure.

Outcome Measures

Modified Oxford Grading System (MOGS) by Laycock to grade the pelvic floor muscles strength; International Consultation Incontinence Questionnaire-Short Form (ICIQ-SF) to measure the severity and impact of urinary incontinence; Incontinence-Quality of Life (I-QOL) to measure the quality of life were used as outcome measures. All assessments were carried out by the same physiotherapist before the start of the intervention and after 20 sessions of treatment.

Modified Oxford Grading System

MOGS is widely used by physiotherapists to evaluate the strength of the pelvic floor muscles by using anal digital palpation. It consists of a six-point scale: 0 = no contraction, 1 = flicker, 2 = weak, 3 = moderate, 4 = good (with lift), and 5 = strong. The MOGS scale demonstrates variable reliability with kappa and correlation values ranging from fair to good [6][7].

For digital palpation, the gloved and lubricated index finger of the examiner was introduced into the anus with the patient put in the left lateral position and was commanded to “lift” and “squeeze” the pelvic floor muscles. The felt contraction was graded accordingly. Palpation was performed with one finger because two fingers may stretch the pelvic floor muscles and thereby influence the ability to contract.

International Consultation Incontinence Questionnaire-Short Form

The ICIQ-SF is a brief questionnaire that allows for detecting urinary incontinence as well as its severity, type, and impact on life. It is an objective scale consisting of 4 questions to be answered and graded differently and the total score ranges from 0 to 21; higher scores indicate greater severity. It is one of the most used questionnaires in persons with urinary incontinence with a high test-retest reliability [8].

Incontinence-Quality of Life

The I-QOL specifically measures the quality of life in persons with urinary incontinence. It consists of 22 items, all of which have a value ranging from 1 (extremely) to 5 (not at all). Three subscales can be identified: Limiting behavior consisting of 8 items; Psychosocial impacts with 9 items and Social embarrassment, consisting of 5 items. Although the maximum value is 110, it is transformed into a 0- to 100- point scale for

a better interpretation; a higher score indicates better QOL. I-QOL is a reliable, valid, and responsive measure of the incontinence-related quality of living [9].

Intervention

The intervention protocol consisted of 20 sessions of PFMT with EMG-BFB, which were supervised by a trained physiotherapist and performed 5 days a week for a total of 4 weeks. Each treatment session lasted 30 minutes.

The used equipment was Myomed gymnast, which allows performing EMG-BFB with four channels and delivering both audio and visual signals through a connected laptop, that was subsequently connected to a larger display screen for a comfortable and easy viewing experience of the patient.

At every treatment session, the patient was in a supine position with the lower limbs semi-flexed, facing toward the larger display screen for both visual and auditory feedback. Two self-adhesive electrodes were placed around the anal canal at 3 and 9 hours to record the electrical activity of the pelvic floor muscles and another two self-adhesive electrodes on the rectus abdominis muscle and another indifferent electrode (ground electrode) were placed in the pelvic area distant from the working area. The ground electrode channel was used to avoid the contraction of the nearby musculatures (gluteus and adductors), thus isolating the exclusive work of the pelvic floor musculature [10]. The signal of the muscle activity as recorded, acted as a stimulant for motor learning. The patient performed 105 work/rest cycles of pelvic muscles per session of which the first 5 work/rest cycles were averaged, the mean value in micro-volt (μV) was determined and added with not more than $25\mu\text{V}$ to set the target to be achieved on that very session. Work lasted 7 seconds and then rest for 4 seconds.

Results

The results have been presented in tabular form for visual analysis which is as follows after 2 sessions of intervention.

According to the modified oxford grading scale, the digital anal palpation was scored as “2” which states ‘weak muscle activity without a circular contraction’ before the intervention, and was subsequently graded as “3” implying ‘moderate muscle contraction’ post-intervention. This shows an improvement in the pelvic floor muscle contraction (Table 01).

Urinary incontinence ICIQ-SF also showed improvement with a total score of 19 pre-intervention to 15 post-intervention suggesting of decrease in the severity of the incontinence (Table 01). Though the amount of urine leakage decreased and its interference with everyday life also improved; there was no change in the frequency of the leakage after 20 sessions of intervention.

The quality of life of the subject also got better following the intervention as measured by the I-QOL. The subscale scores of limiting behavior; psychological impacts and social embarrassment rose from 37.5, 33.3, and 23.3 to 42.5, 46.7, and 46.7 respectively after 20 sessions while the total scale score rose from 33.6 to 47.3 (Table 01).

Discussion

Several interesting findings have emerged from this case study. There occurred a significant decrease in symptoms along with improvement in muscle strength as well as an increase in the standard of the quality of life, according to the Modified oxford grading scale, ICIQ-SF, and I-QOL suggesting that this behavior-based treatment of PFMT with EMG-BFB has a significant role in the management of stress urinary incontinence.

The application of PFMT with EMG-BFB has been extensively studied in the case of females with genuine stress incontinence [11] and in the case of males with stress incontinence following prostatectomy and incomplete spinal cord injury [12]. In most of those, it is well documented that the effect of PFMT with EMG-BFB is effective in the treatment of SUI and regaining of the continence [13]. In accordance with those studies, the result of this case study also demonstrated the effectiveness of PFMT with EMG-BFB in the treatment of SUI and in improving the quality of life following CNS and PNS vasculitis.

A few other studies involving treatment of incontinence with PFMT assisted by EMG-BFB also disprove its utility and contradict the result as that of ours showing a non-significant effect in the reduction of the symptoms and in the improvement of the quality of life [14].

A possible cause of such improvement in the pelvic floor muscle strength and the effect of incontinence on the quality of life could be that biofeedback provided a mechanism for the client to identify the appropriate muscle to concentrate the contraction at, as well as a sense of accomplishment as he increased his contraction scores over the predecided EMG score. Moreover, this PFMT technique facilitates learning and creates a sense of strong motivation that helps with clinical improvement [15].

This study had a pre-determined protocol of EMG-BFB-assisted PFMT for the management of stress incontinence in CNS and PNS vasculitis which resulted in a significant improvement in signs and symptoms for 20 consecutive sessions. But its effectiveness was not assessed in the follow-up, so future studies may focus on determining adequate treatment protocol to analyze the physical and behavioral treatment effect of the EMG-BFB when used as adjunctive therapy and should focus on ascertaining whether a significant differential effect occurs according to symptom severity.

Conclusion

This study, hence concludes that the stress incontinence associated with CNS and PNS vasculitis can be benefited by PFMT with the EMG-BFB management program alone or in adjunct with other treatments. A single case study is suitable for an in-depth investigation of the management of an individual subject thus it was chosen as the design of the study, so the results of such a study should not be generalized to the population as a whole.

Ethical Approval

Written consent was obtained from the patient.

Conflict of Interest

None declared.

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Table 01: Outcome measures before and after treatment sessions

Outcome Measures	At the start of the treatment sessions	At the end of the treatment sessions
MOGS	Grade 2	Grade 3
ICIQ-SF	19	15
I-QOL	33..6	47.3